

Short communication

**First report of *Camponotidea saundersi*
(Hemiptera, Heteroptera, Miridae) from Iran**

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اولین گزارش از *Camponotidea saundersi* (Hemiptera, Heteroptera, Miridae)

برای ایران

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چکیده

مطالعه فونستیک روی سن‌های میریده در بخش غربی استان کردستان طی سال‌های ۲۰۱۶-۲۰۱۷ انجام شد. از نمونه‌های جمع‌آوری شده گونه *Camponotidea saundersi* (Puton, 1874) برای اولین بار در ایران گزارش می‌شود. در این مطالعه، توصیف جنس نر و ماده این گونه و کلید شناسایی برای گونه‌های گزارش شده جنس *Camponotidea* از ایران ارائه شده است. نمونه‌های جمع‌آوری شده در کلکسیون حشرات موزه تاریخ طبیعی دانشگاه گیلان نگاه‌داری می‌شوند. **واژگان کلیدی:** فون، ایران، کلیدی شناسایی، سن‌های برگی

دریافت: ۱۳۹۶/۱۰/۶، پذیرش: ۱۳۹۷/۳/۵.

Plant bugs of Miridae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) are one of the most species rich families of insects, with nearly 11020 described species (Cassis & Schuh, 2012). This family includes eight subfamilies. The subfamily Mirinae comprises many species and genera. The genus *Camponotidea* belongs to the subfamily Mirinae, with the following taxonomic characteristics; body shape elongated, like a large ant, similar to the *Messor* Forel or *Camponotus* Mayr (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) (Wagner, 1974), abdomen oval, rostrum short, reaches to the front or middle coxa, body color black or brownish. Only two species, including *C. fieberi* and *C. saundersi* has been recognized so far in this genus around the world, occurring in the Mediterranean region (Puton, 1874, Reuter, 1879, Tamanini, 1981, Wagner, 1974). Linnavuori in 2009 reported *C. fieberi* from the Azerbaijan-e Gharbi, Iran (Linnavuori, 2009). This is the first report of *C. saundersi* from Iran.

The collected specimens were killed by ethyl acetate, transferred to the laboratory, and mounted on triangular card. Male genitalia were dissected in glycerol. Photographs of specimens were taken using a Canon EOS 70D camera equipped by a canon EF 100mm f/2.8 Macro USM macro lens. All photos were combined in Helicon Focus software (ver. 6.7.1). Collected specimens were deposited at the Natural History Museum of the University of Guilan.

Key to the species of *Camponotidea* found in Iran

1. The apex of labium reaches to the mesocoxa. Body Size (♂) 7.05 mm, first and second antennal segment (♂) 0.7: 3.33mm. Body color black. Hind tibia (♂) 5.13× as long as pronotum at the base. *Camponotidea saundersi*
2. The labium extends to procoxa or slightly beyond it. Body size (♂) 9.15 mm, first and second antennal segment (♂) 0.83: 3.67mm. Body color brown. Hind tibia (♂) 6.4× as long as pronotum at the base. *Camponotidea fieberi*

Camponotidea saundersi (Puton, 1874)

Material examined. Kurdistan province: Dezli; Sarvabad 3♂, 2♀ (35°22'N 46°12'E, 1299m), 15.5.2017. Bahram Abad; Sarvabad 3♂, 5♀ (35°22'N 46°14'E, 1,199m), 28.5.2017. Daraki; Sarvabad 4♂, 4♀ (35°19'N 46°10'E, 1,765m), 31.5.2017.

Diagnosis: Body shape antlike, elongated. Male smaller than female; body size (♂) 7.05mm, (♀) 8.67mm (Fig. 1 A, B, D). Both sexes brachypterous, black species. Apex of second antennal segment thick. Pronotum narrower than head width; 0.65-0.75× as long as head.

Head black. Eyes brownish black or reddish brown. Antennal segment yellowish brown to brownish black, Apex of second antennal segment black and covered by short setae. Labium black. Scutellum black and wider than posterior margin of pronotum. Brachypterous hemelytra black, distal margin with a yellow transverse stripe. Abdomen black, first abdominal segment yellow. Legs black, tibia yellowish brown.

Body covered by long setae. Head large and elongated, oblique. Vertex flat, without groove. Eyes removed from anterior margin of pronotum. Pronotum anteriorly convex, posteriorly constricted, without collar and calli. Propleuron with deep groove, visible from dorsal view. First labium segment thick, the apex of labium reaches to the mesocoxa. Abdomen oval. Legs strong, long with slender hair, tibia covered with dark spin-like setae.

Body size (♂) 7.05, (♀) 8.67mm; Ocular index (♂) 2.37, (♀) 2.86; Base of pronotum 1.03-1.1mm; Base of pronotum 1× as long as interior of pronotum; Base of pronotum 0.67×- 0.72× as long as width of the head; Proportions among antennal segments (♂) 0.7: 3.33: 1.66: 1.05, (♀) 0.8 :3.56 :1.86 :1.16; 2nd antennal segment (♂) 2.17×, (♀) 2.27× as long as width of head; 2nd antennal segment 3.22- 3.25× as long as base of pronotum.

Genital segment (♂) small. Lateral margin of right paramere wrinkled with bristles. Left paramere hook-shaped, apophysis with bristle like setae. Endosoma small, simple, without spicule, membranous, secondary gonopore normal.

Comment: This species has been collected on different host plants such as *Secale ciliatiglume* (Poaceae), *Echinops* sp. (Asteraceae) and *Trifolium* sp. (Liguminous). Found in Albania, Croatia, Turkey, Greece, Slovenia, Macedonia, Montenegro and Italy (Aukema & Rieger, 1999; Josifov & Simov, 2006).

***Camponotidea fieberi* (Reuter, 1879)**

Diagnosis: Slightly larger than previous species. Body size (♂) 9.15mm, color brown. Pronotum, scutellum, brachypterus hemelytra and legs are reddish brown (Fig1 C, E). Antennal segments brownish yellow, pale, apex of second antennal segment thick, black. Labium short, extend to procoxa or partly beyond it.

Body size (♂) 9.15 mm; Ocular index (♂) 2.5; Base of pronotum 1.03-1.1mm; Base of pronotum 1× as long as interior of pronotum; Base of pronotum 0.68× as long as width of the head; Proportions among antennal segments (♂) 0.83: 3.67: 1.87: 1.1; 2nd antennal segment (♂) 2.4× as long as width of head; 2nd antennal segment 3.49× as long as base of pronotum.

Comments: The collected specimen belongs to var. *simulans* Horváth, 1918. Found on *Salvia* sp. and *Vicia* sp. in steppes. Anatolian, known from Greece, Turkey Iraq and Iran (Linnavuori 2009).

Fig. 1. *Camponotidea* species: (A, B, D) *C. saundersi*; A& D ♀, B ♂. (C, E) *C. fieberi*; C&E ♂, A-C dorsal view, D-E lateral view.

References

- Aukema, B. & Rieger, C.** (1999) *Catalogue of the Heteroptera of the Palaearctic Region*, Vol. 3. The Netherlands Entomological Society, 577 pp.
- Carvalho, J. C. M.**, (1959) *A catalogue of the Miridae of the world*. Part IV. Arquiyo do Museu Nacional, Rio de Janeiro 48, 1-384
- Cassis, G. & Schuh, R. T.** (2012) Systemetic, biodiversity, biogeography, and host associations of the Miridae (Insecta: Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Cimicomorpha). *The Annual review of Entomology* 57, 377- 404
- Josifov, M., & Simov, N.** (2006) Endemism among the Heteroptera on the Balkan Peninsula. *Landesmuseen Neue Serie* 50, 879–898
- Linnavuori, R. E.** (2009) Studies on the Nepomorpha, Gerromorpha, Leptopodomorpha and Miridae excluding Phylini (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) of Khuzestan and the adjacent provinces of Iran. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* 49 (1), 1-32.
- Puton, A.** (1874). Hémiptères nouveaux (suite). *Petites Nouvelles Entomologiques* 1, 439-440.
- Reuter, O. M.** (1879) Till kändedom om mimiska Hemiptera och deras lefnadshistoria. *Öfversigt af Finska Vetenskaps societetens Förhandlingar* 21, 141-198

- Tamanini, L.** (1981) Gli eterotteri della Basilicata e della Calabria (Italia Meridionale): (Hemiptera Heteroptera). *Museo civico di storia naturale di Verona, sr. 2, 3*, 1-164
- Wagner, E.** (1974) Die Miridae Hahn, 1831, des Mittelmeerraumes und der Makaronesischen Inseln (Hemiptera, Heteroptera). Teil. 1. *Entomologische Abhandlungen 37 Suppl. iii* + 484
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